

THE ROLE OF NATIONAL SPIRITUAL VALUES IN THE FORMATION OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10403127>

Abstract. *The article indicates that the educational process at primary school age is of leading importance, providing students with the opportunity to master methods for solving various spiritual and moral problems, the role of national values in the formation of future primary school teachers.*

Keywords: *primary school, educational process, knowledge, intellectual, moral, problems, development, future primary school teachers, formation.*

The problem of the role of national spiritual values and moral education in human life is studied and researched by philosophers, psychologists and pedagogues - scientists. Nevertheless, this problem is a topical issue from today's point of view. The mission of a modern comprehensive school is to educate a responsible citizen who can independently evaluate the events happening in the world and is able to build his daily activities in accordance with the interests of the people around him. The solution to this problem is related to the development of stable national moral values in students. The main thing is to form students' intellectual, emotional, loyalty to national spiritual values, business and communicative readiness for active interaction with the outside world.

The issue of bringing up a person in the spirit of loyalty to national spiritual values and bringing them to maturity is considered an urgent issue in our society and has always been a concern. Especially now, when harshness and violence are common, the issue of developing national moral values is becoming increasingly important.

Inadequate demand for the development of national spiritual values causes various levels of conflicts in everyday life. In finding a solution to this problem, a student - a future teacher, who has the opportunity to influence the education of the young generation, plays an important role. Commenting on national moral values in his research, researcher J. Tokhirov said, "In the conditions of globalization, material borders become more and more relative, and spiritual values gradually become common. In such a period, the concepts of preserving national identity, realizing and appreciating national identity become a priority goal. The process of realizing and appreciating national identity serves as the foundation of our spiritual values" [3]. Therefore, in the future, students should rely on children's intelligence, national values and moral qualities to find solutions to educational problems at school, and be ready to closely help each student in determining the foundations of our moral values. Education in the spirit of loyalty to national moral values, which is an integral part of the educational process, helps to solve this problem.

V.A. Sukhomlinsky emphasizes that in order to educate a child morally, it is necessary to teach him "the ability to feel the person" [p. 6:67-68]. He believes that "a solid foundation of moral belief can be built in childhood and early adolescence, in the period of learning to see, act, and observe good and bad, honor and dishonor, justice and injustice" [6: p. 68].

The school is the main link in the system of educating the young generation, developing in the spirit of loyalty to national spiritual values. At each stage of a child's upbringing, a specific

aspect of education prevails. Researcher Yu.K. Babansky, touching on the role of moral education: children learn simple standards of morality, learn to follow them in different situations. The educational process is closely related to moral education. The role of the educational process in the national spiritual and moral education is increasing in the conditions of the modern school, where the volume of the educational content is increasing and its internal structure is becoming more complicated. He states that the content of moral concepts is related to the knowledge that students acquire through studying academic subjects [2:5 p.].

At the primary school age, the educational process is of leading importance, it ensures the assimilation of knowledge based on a certain system, it creates opportunities for students to master the methods of solving various mental and moral problems.

The role of teachers in educating schoolchildren in the spirit of loyalty to national moral values, developing them, preparing them for life and social work is of primary importance. The teacher is always an example of manners for students and forms a selfless attitude to work. At the current stage of society's development, the moral problems of schoolchildren become especially urgent, and only teachers with national moral values have the ability to solve them. Many social conditions and biological factors affect the spiritual and moral formation of a person, but pedagogical factors play a decisive role in this process, because they are aimed at the development of certain types of relationships.

We all know that one of the important tasks of education is the proper organization of the child's activities. Qualities specific to national spiritual values are formed in the child's activities and can affect the changes in the goals and motives of his relationships that appear in his daily life. The activity of people in the society also serves as a criterion of its spiritual and moral maturity.

To develop the child's national moral values and moral consciousness, by perceiving and understanding the content of the influences caused by parents and teachers, the people around him, and by adapting these influences to the individual's moral experience, his views and national moral values occurs through processing in connection with directions. In his research, researcher M.Akramov focused on the development of national spiritual values, "Important means of education to fully satisfy the spiritual needs of young people: press, television, cinema, theater, literature, music, painting and sculpture, to the internet system of information media, in general, it is necessary to raise to a new level of quality all areas that can directly affect the human heart and thinking" [5].

In this regard, motivations for behavior, decision-making, and the child's choice of actions are formed. The direction of school education and children's actions in this regard may not be enough, but the fundamental meaning of education is to achieve compatibility between the requirements of correct behavior and internal preparation for it.

According to the scientists of the field, knowledge about the national spiritual and moral principles and norms of the society, which the child should master, is a necessary link of the process of moral education. Awareness of moral principles and norms, experience is directly related to knowledge of moral behavior patterns and helps to form moral values and actions.

Most of the children come to the first grade from pre-school educational institutions, where we have mentioned that children acquire enough moral ideas, understanding of national values and customs. Children develop a broad understanding of what is good and what is bad, and how to be kind to others. Children's desire to become schoolchildren is a good incentive for moral education. When children come to school, their range of communication and tasks expands. National spiritual

and moral education is the beginning of all foundations, depending on what the teacher puts into the heart of the child of this age, it affects what kind of person the child will grow up to be in the future, how he will interact with others. That is why it is necessary to take into account their age and psychological characteristics when working on the problems of raising schoolchildren in the spirit of national values.

H. Jabborov, who conducted research on the studied topic, said in his research, "Spiritual education is of great importance in the education of our youth. The most important thing is to pay attention to the upbringing of our children. "It is the basis of germination" [7].

In fact, taking into account the age of children, national norms of moral and ethical behavior can be divided into the following levels: a child under the age of 5 learns primitive rules of behavior based on the prohibition or rejection of something. If a baby is taught to follow these elementary standards, others will consider that baby to be a well-behaved child. By the age of 10-11, a teenager should take into account the situation of people around him, and the presence of these situations can not only interfere with them, but also be pleasant.

For young children, there may be a conflict between knowing the right way and being able to apply it (this applies to etiquette, national values, good behavior, communication). Knowledge of moral and ethical norms and rules of behavior does not always correspond to the actual actions of the child. Especially, this often happens in cases where there is a discrepancy between spiritual and moral standards and the personal wishes of the child. The development of spiritual and moral education is carried out in all classes at school. There are no main and non-main subjects in this regard. It is not only the content, methods and organization of teaching, the teacher, his personality, knowledge, the development of national spiritual values, beliefs, but also the atmosphere formed in the lesson, the style of relations between the teacher and children, and children educates. The teacher educates himself, turns from an object into a subject of education. The student's developmental activity, consciousness, initiative in the learning process is the mastery of his own behavior.

It is important for students to organize this process as a collective activity imbued with high moral attitudes in their future teaching activities and moral education. The influence of the team on the individual is considered optimal when each child takes a place in the team that corresponds to his abilities, becomes an irreplaceable person. Community education puts the student, even the youngest, above the need for basic self-education, without which development, including moral development, is considered impossible.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev said, "If the body of society is the economy, then its soul and spirit is spirituality. When we decide to build a new Uzbekistan, we rely on two strong pillars. The first is a strong economy based on market principles. The second is strong spirituality based on the rich heritage of our ancestors and national values" [1].

To reform higher education in the pedagogical direction in the Republic of Uzbekistan, to be an independent thinker in universities, able to analyze the pedagogical situation, to plan and implement the educational process, to create a friendly atmosphere in the classroom, to monitor and evaluate students, includes the goals of training teachers who are able to effectively train their activities. Such requirements imposed by the society on highly educated specialists have led to a significant increase in the qualifications of teachers in recent years.

A modern teacher should be a creative person, professional, reflect great pedagogical skills, and have developed spiritual abilities. The environment that forms national spiritual values and

culture is represented by extracurricular activities, the educational activities of the university and departments, the conducting of educational activities together with the exercises in the physical education areas of the university have an important impact on the development of these qualities in students.

Extracurricular activities of summer student groups, student sports clubs, student groups and theaters, themed parties, etc. serve as means of developing future teachers' national spiritual values. In this regard, extracurricular activities also create wide opportunities and affect the formation of the educational potential of students at the university. The forms of these processes are diverse, and they can include: student scientific and practical conferences, pedagogical skill competitions, holidays organized in the city, sports events, labor landings, collective creative activities, etc.

Philosopher-scientist Q. Nazarov "It is always important for the nation to fulfill itself, that is, to ensure the future of the nation, to preserve its customs, traditions, language, cultural and spiritual wealth will continue to be" [p. 8:56], emphasizing the importance of developing the national spiritual values of the Uzbek people.

Therefore, the gallery of portraits of our national heroes, great scientists, the figures of our famous teachers of the past and present, instills a sense of pride in students, instills in them love for the educational institution, high scientific aspirations, self-demanding, moral motivates the formation of positions, development of professional ideals, sense of patriotism, national spiritual values, general and special professional cultures. Pedagogical conditions for the formation of educational potential are different, student debates, mutual relations between students and the university administration; includes self-management of students, activities of the center for social and psychological support for students. At this point, we believe that the systematic educational process at the university should consist of the following: first of all, in order to create conditions for the comprehensive educational impact on the student, the following components for the development of the student's personality: professional knowledge and personal qualities, conscientiousness; social attractiveness; unity of word and deed; physical, mental and moral health; education; general cultural literacy; creativity; communication; self control; independence. J. Tohirov, one of the researchers conducting research in the field, said, "When it comes to the spiritual values of our nation, patriotism, friendship, peace-loving, hospitality, hard work, kindness, concern, honor, honesty, kindness have been created for centuries. "Finally, it is necessary to mention good human qualities such as brotherhood and good neighborly relations" [3].

Therefore, it is worth emphasizing once again that national spiritual values play a big role in human life. As a result of adult intervention, young students often understand what they are learning. These are: Attitude towards oneself. Prudence or self-love, self-respect or pride, in relationships with other people, arrogance or acceptance, mercy or cruelty, kindness or cruelty, humanity or betrayal, sincerity or hypocrisy, respect for people or arrogance. In relation to activity, organization or carelessness, diligence or laziness, responsibility or carelessness, self-control and courage or cowardice, kind leadership or passivity. In relation to property, thrift or greed, generosity or greed, envy or selflessness.

The problems of national moral values are reflected in many programs for primary schools. For a child, the spiritual image of a person is not the main thing. For them, a decent person means a more handsome, intelligent, obedient person. They do not have such qualities as honesty,

fairness, responsibility, sensitivity, politeness. Unfortunately, taking this into account, adults do not always take the right approach. Often, schoolchildren can show rudeness, arrogance, and disrespect without feeling the need to observe moral and ethical standards. Sometimes this situation can make teachers feel powerless.

The reasons for lack of spirituality in children can be different. Parents and teachers think about it as follows: how to educate a spiritually mature person; how to teach children to follow these norms; how to explain the meaning of these norms to them; when to start parenting. Everyone is interested in the following question: what kind of art is necessary to raise a modern child without shouting, slapping and punishment? In fact, here we are talking about the problems of developing national moral values in children, developing the regulation of self-behavior in accordance with established norms and rules, turning them into internal guidelines, and forming an empathic attitude towards them.

The effectiveness of national moral values is determined by children's adherence to moral norms, contrary to their own interests, without adult control or coercion, especially in the conditions of free moral choice, when there is a temptation to violate them. Today, schoolchildren spend most of their time on smartphones, tablets, and computers, and their human relationships are not developed. Solving these relations is the "new old" problem of developing national moral values of modern elementary school students.

The origin of value should be sought in why a person comes to this world in the first place, what is his purpose. The answers to these questions are closely related to the concept of spirituality, because there are no satisfactory concepts in this regard in the materialistic picture of the world. Spirituality is the ability to identify, choose and adhere to values. Spirituality is filling a child's life with meaning in everything. It is on the national spiritual basis that moral qualities have meaning and purpose, and a list of qualities that adults want to see in a child appears. The child understands why he needs to cultivate good qualities in himself and tries not only to behave well externally, but also to be this way in his inner life. Appeal to national moral values creates internal motivation to learn good behavior. Therefore, the future teacher should take into account that various character qualities are formed in a child in several stages.

The child knows what is good and what is bad, the ability to distinguish between them in different situations. In addition, the child's desire for spirituality and the formation of a personal emotional relationship is important.

Elementary school students, being emotional and curious about everything new, have a high confidence and lively attitude towards works of art. Nature, with its variety and splendor, logic and laws, is an excellent teacher. All this is enough to understand the human word, starting from the moment when the child begins to perceive fairy tales and stories. Therefore, it is appropriate to start taking care of national spiritual education from this moment.

Future teachers, when a child does not have any responsibilities in the family until the age of adolescence, does not know where everything comes from and is used only to satisfy his own needs, joy, sorrow and hardship. If they are not used to sharing with the whole family, they should understand that they will grow up selfish in the family and organize their activities. Sometimes parents try to satisfy all the whims of their children. As a result, children become selfish. The child should know what funds are needed to support the family, where their parents work, how much they earn, and how important their work is to society.

The child needs to know what his father, mother and other family members need, because if necessary, they can refuse to meet some of their needs. The child should understand that his well-being depends on the work of each family member. Another of the qualities of patriotism is a sense of honor as a national spiritual value. It arises in the family, in the daily life of the child. A student who respects his parents, school, and class does not want his family and school to be blamed. Teachers and parents should use all means to develop a sense of honor in students and fight their ambitions. Paying attention to the child's positive actions plays an important role in developing a sense of honor.

A future teacher should know how to teach a child to feel responsible for his actions. Deliberate failure or intentional damage to something must be punished. But we cannot punish for every unfinished business, for every broken thing. It is an important tool to reliably explain how the child's irresponsibility, carelessness, careless attitude to things caused harm, and to show the consequences of their carelessness. If parents and teachers always do the unfinished work of the child themselves, cover the damage caused by their children, children will develop an absolutely irresponsible attitude towards business and the product.

It is very important to teach the child to be disciplined: come home immediately after school, take off the school uniform and put on home clothes; make sure to wash your hands before eating. It is important to teach him to go for a walk at a certain time and to do his homework. As a result of the repetition of such actions, habits will appear in the child, which will free the parents from the need to constantly remind and teach them.

We believe that the most important task for the development of education in the 21st century is to teach people to live together, to help them transform the existing interdependence of states and ethnic groups into a conscious unity. For these purposes, education should, on the one hand, help a person to understand his roots and thereby determine his place in the world, and on the other hand, to inculcate respect for other cultures.

Human potential for continuous development is a natural process. The development of mental functions takes place under the influence of social relations that arise spontaneously in the course of physiological development and purposeful influences that stimulate or slow down the development of a person during life. Development happens like the replacement of the old with the new, repeated "negations". Self-development of a person is determined by his needs and motives, therefore, the most important pedagogical task in the development of a person, including national spiritual and moral education, is self-development in relation to citizenship in the process of self-realization. is to provide positive motivation.

One of the important problems in pedagogy, which researchers constantly return to, is the problem of the relationship between child education and development. Changing the educational model, from the point of view of spiritual and moral education, the implementation of a person-oriented approach in the organization of the pedagogical process requires a review of the goals, tasks, and functions of the activity. This is very slow and not always effective in practice. In adults, the development of national spiritual values at the required level awakens moral concepts such as honor, justice, selflessness in supporting good ideas in children.

The future teacher is the main person in the education of students in the spirit of peace and humane inter-ethnic dialogue, and actively forms national spiritual values, worldview and morality in the student. Therefore, today, at a new stage of the development of Uzbekistan, we consider it appropriate to take into account the following when defining the ideal of modern national

education: modern national education in connection with the ideals of national education of the past continuity of the lim ideal; National moral and ethical values established in accordance with the current legislation of Uzbekistan; External and internal problems facing Uzbekistan. Increasing the number of multi-ethnic people of Uzbekistan, improving the quality of their life, work and creativity, strengthening national spirituality and morality, citizen solidarity and statehood, developing national culture, national priority. After all, this opinion can be observed in the views of researchers conducting research in the field. For example, researcher M. Boltayev said, "National values are formed based on local and religious values, and universal values are formed based on many national values and continue to improve over the centuries. But even in today's conditions of rapid globalization, any nation that preserves and enriches its national material and spiritual wealth stands out from other nations with its own traditions, customs and immortal values" [4] emphasizes.

The ideal of modern national spiritual values is a highly moral, creative, well-rounded citizen of Uzbekistan, who accepts the fate of the Motherland as his own, feels responsibility for the present and future of his country, the national identity of multinational peoples. based on spiritual and cultural values. The development and upbringing of the student's national moral values begins with this. The values of national spiritual and family life acquired by a child from the first years of his life are of constant importance for a person of any age. Based on family relationships, relationships in society are predicted and form the basis of the child's civil behavior. Our scientific research on the development of national spiritual values of future teachers has shown that the future of the student consists of practical activities rich in creativity, innovation and creativity. A person is formed in the eyes of the teacher. Therefore, it is an important task to form the national moral values of the student who will enter the teaching profession in the future.

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